

DEVELOPING STUDENT'S VOCABULARY BY USING DIRECT LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Abstract: This study explores the direct learning strategies and its 3 main groups as memory, cognitive and compensation strategies. It also aims further exploration and gives clear and thorough explanation of what these group strategies are and how these ones can be used in language education field. Besides, a few particular techniques provided in this article are intended to give a precise example for each of them, so it can help you to be able to differentiate main topic. It also claims how important they are in language learning while maintaining focus precious efforts of learners.

Key words: vocabulary, learning strategy, direct learning strategy, memory strategy, cognitive strategy, compensation strategy, semantic mapping, mnemonics, repetition, spaced learning, code-switching.

Vocabulary learning strategies are the techniques and approaches to help learners acquiring, understanding, and using new words effectively in a target language. In 1990, Oxford revealed two main categories used by learners' strategies: direct and indirect learning strategies that are differed for their own features, techniques, and purpose of learning.

According to N.Schmitt (1997) a direct learning strategy, it is the type of strategy to learn and practice the new words with forced and intentional efforts by structured teaching methods and explicit instructions. It is featured for providing focus on specific words and emphasizing a practice on them to get their meaning, definition thoroughly. It involves consciously training whether under the control of teacher or intentional self-study. The categories help to make the strategies effectual with its systematic as well as flexible approaches. They are divided into 3 main groups:

a) memory;

- b) cognitive;
- c) compensation strategies.

Each of them has their own different structure for different purposes. Memory strategy, like grouping or using imagery, is functioned specifically for retrieving new information. Cognitive strategy to summarize and to reason deductively that enables learners to understand and use new language by different means whereas compensation strategy lets them guess or use synonyms when they have lack of knowledge while using the language.

MEMORY STRATEGY.

Memory strategies, also known as mnemonics, have been used for thousands of years and provided users with satisfied outcomes. The particular reason is that this strategy reflects simple principles connected with our brain and memory, like arranging things in order, making associations, reviewing and etc.

In language learning, we can create a mental linkage by providing visuals with verbal labels or create and visualize image of verbal actions, abstract concepts, phrases and more. Help of connecting words and images offers us richer learning experience by activating both visual and verbal parts of our brain and abstract ideas find their more concrete visual alternatives to help learners to remembering the things faster and for longer period.

Semantic Mapping is type of memory strategy that is considered practical in processes as it involves making association among several related words to the key concept during grouping them with imagery.

Mnemonics is about remembering new words with some tricky ways to remember it with ease and less of effort. It can be making a funny sentence with certain number of target vocabularies. For example, for the vocabularies about 'Travel', "*Packing Bags Really Makes Trips Super Fun*" can be a mnemonic sentence for travel essentials: *Passport, Boarding pass, Reservations, Map, Tickets, Suitcase, Foreign currency*. Or it can be single word form called *acronyms* like *SMART* for *Suitcase, Map, Adapter, Reservation, Tickets*.

COGNITIVE STRATEGIES.

Unlike memory strategies, cognitive strategies require much more effort and intention from learner. as it is about the *four* PRACTical categories:

- a) Practicing;
- b) Receiving and Sending message;
- c) Analyzing and Reasoning;
- d) Creating Structure for Input and Output.

These strategies help to understanding the concepts deeply, to process and retain the knowledge for a longer period after introducing or learning vocabularies briefly. Anderson (2005) also notes that learners who are aware of their cognitive strategies tend to regulate their learning more effectively and demonstrate higher levels of autonomy. Unlikely, just memorizing, learning process is considered as an active learning process, because it is about analyzing the concepts, connecting and applying information. They also have an adaptability to suggest learners use suitable strategies for their individual style, pace or aims.

Practice or Repetition is effective strategy despite its simplicity, serves to retain the information in our long-term memory accurately through continuous repetition of notes, reminders, speeches or video lectures.

Spaced learning. This learning technique is practical with its determined focus to the tasks and learning materials till an appointed break to take some distraction that leads to productivity. (Pomodoro is one of the well-known methods for time management.)

Explaining the topic to somebody. It should not be as complex as your professor does, after gaining the knowledge about topic and finishing learning process, just explaining or discussing that topic with anyone can make the information received retain with better, clear understanding for longer period.

COMPENSATION STRATEGIES.

Compensation strategies are asset of communicative techniques helps to overcome linguistic gaps in their knowledge when communicating. These

strategies enable speakers maintaining communication despite limitations, not only in vocabulary, but also in grammar, or fluency by:

Circumlocution - to describe a concept using alternative words or giving detailed explanation;

Coining words – making up new words to describe the idea, like *flower-pot for vase*;

Gestural communication – using physical motion, such as mime or gestures, to express the meaning;

Code-switching – mainly switched with speaker's mother tongue when equivalent is unknown and words are not directly translated as it can be expressed with only knowing context. *Yesterday, men do 'kongga bordim, but they didn't have what I needed.*

In conclusion, effective language learning needs a strategy besides with effort. As we explored in this article that key techniques of direct learning strategies such as memory, cognitive, compensation, all of which contribute to improved language acquisition and communication skills. By selecting the most suitable strategies, learners can unblock the challenges, gain confidence, and achieve fluency more effectively. Therefore, understanding and applying the strategy is essential for long-term success in language learning.

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